

Nowadays education and long-life learning

Dineva Snejana

Faculty of Techniques and Technology - Yambol, Trakia University of Stara Zagora, "Graf Ignatiev" str. 38, Yambol 8600, BULGARIA, E-mail: sbdineva[at]abv.bg

Abstract

The article reviews the importance of long-life learning nowadays and the new semantic e-learning environment creating during last years to support the requirements of that conditions. The education in 21th century is a long-life learning education with commitment of formal, non-formal and informal learnings supported by New Learning Environments. The e-Academia framework has been adopted and created with real and virtual members of organizations, applications for communication and collaboration, e-Learning and directory services. The aim of article is to describe the changes of education system in the last decades forced by the innovations of technology and their implementation in the life. The characteristics of the New Learning Environments are analyzed and the concept of long-life learning.

Keywords: long-life learning, new learning environments, intelligent network

1. Introduction

The new paradigms accepted in nowadays education, both in higher educational institutions and "in general", in the entire educational system is 'lifelong learning' with the philosophy "education from cradle to grave" (Demirel, 2009). Education is vital for both society and individuals and it must be supported from the cooperation of family, school, environment and mass media (Gulen M., 2015). Today, more than ever, the society and economy rely on highly educated and competent people, and that is a reason for education and training systems to be amended to this reality (EC, 2017). In order to meet the challenges of 21th century, learning became not limited to formal education, but integrated with non-formal and informal learning (<http://lllplatform.eu/who-we-are/about-us/>). The e-Learning became with a wider meaning than before embracing all resources of e-Learning communication and collaboration that are base of creating intelligent communication network or New Learning Environments which maintenance long-life learning of individuals.

The aim of article is to describe the changes of education system in the last decades forced by the innovations of technology and their implementation in the life. The characteristics of the New Learning Environments are analyzed and the concept of long-life learning.

2. Education nowadays

In the context of rapid socio-economic, cultural and technological changes of the world, it is widely acknowledged that individuals should possess unique skills that would allow them to compete in the increasingly globalized world (Mwaikokesya et al., 2014). The concept of education took changes from 20th to 21th century, table 1, as lifelong learning style of learning has been assumed (Longworth 2003).

**Table 1. Differences of the concepts of education between 20th and 21th century
(Longworth, 2003)**

The concept of education -differences	20th century	21th century
<i>Education sets of objectives</i>	narrow academic objectives and targets, works to achieve these in the present	the concept of lifelong learning accepted, works to achieve not only present targets, but also to impart future long term values and attitudes to learning
<i>Relationship with industry</i>	short term business plan usually around academic matters, little effort is made to keep every stakeholder informed and on-side	full written organizational strategy available to all, and proactive information strategies to bring all stakeholders on-side
<i>In-service training of teachers</i>	some teachers go on educational courses according to their needs or desires and there are occasional seminars in schools only for teachers	every person in the school has a continuous improvement plan for academic and personal skill embedded into the management system and as a part they are related to the school development plan
<i>Role of the teacher</i>	teachers are the only human resource for curriculum delivery and other resources are supplied from local government and school events	objected to add human resource by tapping into skills, talents and knowledge of governors, parents and everyone in the community by exploring funding
<i>Curriculum</i>	based on discrete subjects and they are assessed on memorizations of facts with fail-pass philosophy	based on skills and knowledge, the enhancement of self- esteem and the acceptance of lifelong values
<i>Support services</i>	teachers are overworked and sparse support service is given to identify and solve individual learning and social problems	guidance, support and counselling systems are available for all learners and their families
<i>Evaluation</i>	based on examination success	outward to the world and it learns by contributing to the community in which it exists. A strong social curriculum is created to promote a sense of tolerance and understanding of different races, creed and cultures
<i>Instruction methods and techniques</i>	teacher has a role of passer of information through didactic teaching methods using chalk, talk and paper exercises	teacher has a role of developer of learning skills using motivational power of the individualized learning programmes like ICT, multimedia and Networks
<i>Relationshipwithparents</i>	parents are invited to school to discuss the child's progress once a term and there are occasional public information meetings	it is objected to involve the family in to the life of the school through increased home-school cooperation and to develop their awareness about active participation in school events
<i>Schoolactivities</i>	only one show or play once a year and the actives out of school are led by only enthusiastic teachers. Sometimes there are Annual School Fair and Presentation Days	a wide range of extra-curricular activities, impressive programme of school societies, out of school activities, cultures, events should be established and involve the community where is appropriate
<i>Vision of school</i>	high academic achievers in order to enhance attractiveness to parents through position in league tables	concentrated on academic and personal success of all pupils as a means of enhancing the school's reputation and satisfying society's needs. The school should create its own league table of all round achievement

Longworth (2003) also summarizes the barriers that should be overcome to be applied the lifelong learning:

- ✓ *mental barriers* - poor family culture of learning, low aspiration, low self-esteem, bad childhood experience of learning;
- ✓ *financial barriers* - lack of finance to participate, and lack of study facilities at home;
- ✓ *access barriers* - distance to educational provision for a large number of students;
- ✓ *learning design barriers* - learning provision which not geared to the needs and characteristics of lifelong learners and does not sufficiently take into account the individual differences and circumstances of learners during life.
- ✓ *information barriers* - learning providers who supply information which is inadequate in attracting people to learning and fail to ensure that people have access to good-quality advice about learning opportunities throughout their lives.

The barriers can be overcome by the use of new networked learning technologies, providing more and better access to distance education, applying new information and communication technologies (Koper&Tattersall, 2004). Implementing the newest technology affects how we live, work, play, and most notably learn (Mareco, 2017).

The benefits of applying mobile technology in the classroom are described from Mareco (2017):

- ✓ mobile devices and their applications prepare students for the future careers;
- ✓ effective way to connect with students of all learning styles;
- ✓ enhance the interaction with classmates and instructors by encouraging collaboration;
- ✓ opportunity to develop student's digital citizenship skills;
- ✓ helps students stay engaged;
- ✓ combining virtual reality with traditional classroom instruction is a way to enhance the learning experience and create new opportunities;
- ✓ students are able to access the most up-to-date information quicker and easier;
- ✓ traditional passive learning model is broken; the teacher becomes the encourager, adviser, and coach;
- ✓ technology helps students be more responsible;
- ✓ transformed the learning experience, empower students to be more creative and connected.

3. The New Learning Environments (NLEs) and long-life learning

3.1. Building the future of education – e-Academia framework

The New Learning Environments (fig.1, NLEs) that respond to the current requirements of education start its development within last 3-4 years with the intensive integration and collaboration of the universities that made e-science community (fig.2), and network, with the help of many projects (Pierre-Yves Burgi, 2012):

- ✓ **IT-Service-** integration designing a future academic environment and combining the virtual and «physical» components, which include studying, teaching, research and administrative aspects. The IT-enhanced environment should be supportive of a variety of teaching scenarios and of Life-Long Learning (LLL).
- ✓ **ScienceWISE-** is a Web-based Interactive Semantic Environment for e-Science in physics, mathematics, biophysics, environmental and computer science. The main goal is to provide a platform for virtual organizations of scientists working together.
- ✓ **Système E-Learning Inductif (SELIN)-** is a project aiming at developing early on at university active learning, teaching of science of observation, and providing teachers and students with multiple opportunities for interaction and empirical investigation. This project is based on pedagogical and epistemological concepts with the use of multimedia tools,

targeted exercises, and a high degree of interactivity to enhance students' learning to develop the following abilities: *topay attention to the obvious, which is core to a strict scientific method; understand a given situation through audio-visual content; compare and contrast different scales of analysis, frameworks of analysis (individual, group, institutional) and methods of data acquisition (simple observation, interaction, interviews, data manipulation).*

- ✓ **Lifelong Learning Transfer (LLL-Transfer)** - the project review existing LLL strategies and organizations and related services and proposed guidelines and checklists for the implementation of LLL.
- ✓ **Personal Learning Environment (PLE) and e-Portfolio** - the objective is to put together institutional and non-institutional tools, to support formal and informal learning. An institutional PLE enabler (iPLEe) to bridge personal, institutional and worldwide resources to enable collaborations between co-learners and sharing of resources; provide students with a set of learning tools, both formal and informal, linking together institutional tools (eg. Moodle, Chamilo, Mediaserver, etc.) and non-institutional tools (eg. Youtube, twitter, Google docs, etc.).

Figure 1. Tree Representation of the NLEs.

Figure 2. e-Academia framework

The e-Academia framework contains (fig.2): *members of real and virtual organizations; applications: for communication, collaboration, e-Learning and other areas; middleware: authentication, security, directory services (one middleware component, mentioned as AAI); infrastructure: an intelligent and transparent network between components.*

3.2. Lifelong Learning - the most important competencies that people must possess

Lifelong learning is now recognized by educators, governing bodies, accreditation organizations, certification boards, employers, third-party payers, and the general public as one of the most important competencies that people must possess (Dam, 2018). The competences learned in formal education need to be developed in order to be adequate during entire life, and keep the competences up to date, to obtain new ones in response to changing needs, and that is a reason to become an autodidact, which is a lifelong process. The concept of lifelong learning has been adopted with the necessity to adjust to the requirements of the knowledge society in the 21st century and to cope with the rapid changes in science and technology (Demirel, 2009). If you want to keep your attitude or to become the best, you can to adopt a mindset of lifelong learning (Brett & McKay, 2018).

The high-quality of education and inclusive lifelong learning is at the heart of the solution of nowadays growing populism, xenophobia, spreading of fake news, high youth unemployment (David Lopez, LLL platform - activity report 2017). The first principle of European Pillar of Social Rights states that everyone has the right to quality and inclusive education, training and lifelong learning to maintain and acquire skills that allow full participation in society and successful transitions in the labour market (EC, 2018).

3.3. Free resources supporting long-life learning

Nowadays the new job skills can be learned inexpensively online, the interactive learning communities are already built by online education companies that transformed education (Pearce, 2017). There are huge available free online courses, which supports long-life learning (Brett & McKay 2018; Cobb, 2017; Jane, 2018; Pearce, 2017):

- ✓ **Blinkist** – free data base for non-fiction books - business, philosophy, history, and more;
- ✓ **Coursera** - the largest course platform for Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) with over 25 million students around the world. It works with top universities from around the world and offer the best online courses for free;
- ✓ **edX** - non-profit source and a leading provider of free courses and training from Harvard University and MIT;
- ✓ **Udacity** - similar to edX and Coursera with the focus on STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) disciplines. Founded by Sebastian Thrun, the creator of Google's self-driving cars. College level classes taught online for free.
- ✓ **MIT Open Courseware** – an ambitious project, all of MIT's courses are available on the web for free;
- ✓ **OpenStudy** - a social learning network that connect individuals with the same learning goals;
- ✓ **Khan Academy** - videos covering almost all academic topics for free.
- ✓ **Duolingo** – free website to learn foreign languages, offers online courses for over 30 languages;
- ✓ **Code Academy** - learn to code for free with interactive exercises;
- ✓ **Wolfram MathWorld** – extensive math resource from all over the world, include information about algebra, geometry, calculus, applied mathematics, discrete mathematics, number theory, statistics, and other math topics;

- ✓ **Open Course Ware (OCW) Consortium** –a collaboration of more than 200 higher education institutions, an excellent place to find free courses and course materials from some of the world’s best colleges and universities;
- ✓ **Lecturefox** –an online directory of free audio, video, and text-based lectures from universities like MIT and Yale;
- ✓ **LearnOutLoud** – contains more than 20 000 free educational materials, including books, videos, audio lectures, and podcasts;
- ✓ **CreativeLive**- the live stream of courses for free, but if you want to view the course later and at your own pace you have to pay for it. The courses focus on more creative and business subjects like videography and online marketing.
- ✓ **TED**–offers lectures by professors and interesting people on different subjects. TED also has several related channels on YouTube, one of which is TED-Ed that offers online lessons on various subjects including history, science, philology and many more, and can be interesting for children as well;
- ✓ **Saylor**– the Saylor Foundation is a non-profit that provides a free University education.
- ✓ **iTunes U** - free podcast lectures by the best professors from around the world;
- ✓ **Project Gutenberg** - offers over 5000 free eBooks, from the classics of literature to the textbooks on specific subjects with impeccable quality;
- ✓ **The Online Books Page** – the University of Pennsylvania’s Online Books Page is one of the best places to find free unabridged books online;
- ✓ **The Free Library** – Farlex’s Free Library contains more than five million books and articles that can be viewed online for free;
- ✓ **YouTube EDU**–contain thousands of videos that cover a variety of topics.

Conclusion

Building the new learning environments and implementation of newest technology in education is a main trend of education nowadays, which requires a long-life learning to be accepted and developed. Long-life learning is the main key that can keep the person on the attitude to the position and degree that hold, and that is ruled by the fast changes of socio-economics, which became a digital economics.

References

- Brett & Kate McKay, (2018): How and Why to Become a Lifelong Learner. A Man's Life, Personal Development. <https://www.artofmanliness.com/articles/how-and-why-to-become-a-lifelong-learner/>
- Burgi Pierre-Yves, (2012): New learning environments. <https://ciel.unige.ch/2012/03/new-learning-environments/>
- Bushati J., E. Lezha, E. Hasmujaj, G. Tuxhari (2017): About digital culture and education. <https://hrcak.srce.hr/file/271706>
- Cobb J., (2017): 25 Free Online Resources and Web Apps for Lifelong Learners. <https://www.missiontolearn.com/lifelong-learner-free-resources/>
- Dam, (2018): <http://www.tesol.org/docs/default-source/new-resource-library/symposium-on-student-empowerment-8.pdf?sfvrsn=0>
- Demirel M., (2009): Lifelong learning and schools in the twenty-first century. *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences* 1 (2009) 1709–1716.
- EC (2018): COUNCIL RECOMMENDATION on Key Competences for Lifelong Learning, <https://ec.europa.eu/education/sites/education/files/recommendation-key-competences-lifelong-learning.pdf>
- European Commission (2017): White Paper on the Future of Europe, https://ec.europa.eu/commission/white-paper-future-europereflexions-and-scenarios-eu27_en
- Gulen M., (2015): The main duty and purpose of human life is to seek understanding. Education from cradle to grave. https://www.newvision.co.ug/new_vision/news/1319253/education-cradle-grave

- Jane K. (2018): 7 Online Tools for Lifelong Learning. <https://blog.peopleperhour.com/blogroll/lifelong-learning-tools/>
- Koper R., C. Tattersall, (2004): New directions for lifelong learning using network technologies. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, Vol 35 No 6 2004, 689-700.
- Longworth N (2003): *Lifelong Learning in Action: Transforming Education in the 21st Century* Kogan Page, London.
- Lopez D., LLLplatform - activity report 2017.
- Mareco Danny (2017): 10 Reasons Today's Students NEED Technology in the Classroom. <https://www.securedgenetworks.com/blog/10-reasons-today-s-students-need-technology-in-the-classroom>
- Mwaikoesya M. J.D., Osborne M., Houston M. (2014): Mapping lifelong learning attributes in the context of higher education institutions. DOI: 10.7227/JACE.20.2.3 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/276681843_Mapping_lifelong_learning_attributes_in_the_context_of_higher_education_institutions
- Pearce K., (2017): 100+ self-education resources for lifelong learning online. <https://www.diygenius.com/100-self-education-resources-for-lifelong-learners/>
- Simmons Michael, (2018): The secret to lifelong success is lifelong learning. <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2018/01/the-secret-to-lifelong-success-is-lifelong-learning>.